

D10.2: Communication activities: first year of VALUEWASTE project

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1 COORDIN.	Centro Tecnológico de la Energía y el Medio Ambiente	CETENMA	ES	RTO
2	Eurizon S.L.	INNOVARUM	ES	SME
3	Savonia University of Applied Sciences - Savonia-ammattikorkeakoulu oy	Savonia	FI	University
4	Servicios Urbanos de Murcia, S.A.U.-Servicios Ferroviales	MU-FERROVIAL	ES	Large Company
5	Ayuntamiento de Murcia	MURCIA	ES	Municipality
6	Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón	ITAInnova	ES	RTO
7	Unibio A/S	Unibio	DK	SME
8	Agro Business Park A/S	ABP	DK	Company cluster
9	Asociación Española de Normalización, (Spanish Association for Standardisation)	UNE	ES	Standardisation body
10	Nutrient Recovery Systems bvba	NuReSys	BE	SME
11	Ekobalans Fenix AB	Ekobalans	SE	SME
12	Ingeniería y Desarrollos Renovables, S.L.	INDEREN	ES	SME
13	GAIKER-IK4 Technology Centre	GAIKER	ES	RTO
14	Entomo Agroindustrial S.L.	ENTOMO	ES	SME
15	Seah International	SEAH	FR	Large Company
16	Kalundborg Kommune	Kalundborg	DK	Municipality
LTP - 16	Kalundborg Symbiose / Symbiosis Center	Symbiosis	DK	Business association
17	European Biomass Industry Association	EUBIA	BE	Industry cluster

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Executive summary

This document is a review of the situation of the Dissemination and Communication Actions of the Valuwaste Project after one year of project execution. It presents the progress for each of the 5 Tasks that make the Work Package 10 (Dissemination & Communication), analyses the situation and describes future steps for these tasks.

*More specifically, **this report focuses** on Tasks 10.1, 10.4 and 10.5: (T10.1) Elaboration of a D&C Plan, (T10.4) Promotion of Results and (T10.5) Communication Actions. Tasks 10.2 and 10.3 (Specific Communication Campaigns) will be further analysed in the Deliverables 10.3 and 10.5.*

*The **main conclusions** of this deliverable (D10.2, Communication activities: first year of VALUEWASTE project) are: **(1)** after one year of project execution (25% of the project), approximately 65% of the numerically measurable indicators established in the D&C Plan (D10.1) are accomplished.*

***(2)** Now that the project steps into a more developed and mature phase, maintaining and increasing growth will prove more challenging. **(3)** However, the start of production of project results, and the development of the Communication Campaigns (Task 10.3 & 10.4) will provide, at the same time, new Dissemination and Communication opportunities.*

***(4)** The communication actions taken during the first 12 months of the project execution were in general relevant to the project and generated a positive impact in its targets. Besides, project partners offered great support and independent initiative in their communication actions, which ultimately is highly beneficial for the communication of the project.*

*Finally, **future steps** established are: increase webpage and blog general content quality and publications length, produce a video presentation of the Valuwaste project, increase collaboration with Valuwaste friend projects (through events, social media or through other means), evaluate the translation of the webpage to Spanish, support the Murcia Communication Campaign and increase results promotion once they start coming out.*

Introduction

This document gathers and describes the main Valuwaste Project activities regarding dissemination and communication within the first year of project execution. Innovarum (the commercial brand of EURIZON S.L., Partner 2) is the Work Package 10 leader (Dissemination and Communication activities).

Innovarum elaborated the Valuwaste Project Communication and Dissemination Plan (D10.1) and oversees the coordination of the different actions that are included in it.

1. Description of work: brief description of tasks

Task 10.1. Development of a Dissemination & Communication Plan (M1-M3)

Responsible partner: Innovarum, Communication Coordinator.

During the first three months of VALUEWASTE project, Innovarum, as Communication coordinator, elaborated **the Dissemination and Communication Plan**. This document corresponded to the deliverable D10.1.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C Plan) is a guide for all dissemination and communication activities that will be carried out by the consortium over the VALUEWASTE project's execution time.

The Plan is made up by two separated but complementary documents: the present "static" document and a "living" Excel document.

- The "static" document collects the objectives for the different dissemination and communication actions, the communication strategy that should be followed, including key messages, tone of communication, online presence and the dissemination kit. It also states the target audiences of the actions, which include general public, policy makers, industry players and the academia, and the different actions, such as website and social media, publications, two communication campaigns, attendance to key events, networking... directed at each one of these collectives. In addition, it includes the project's visual elements as well as templates that will ensure a harmonised communication.
- The "living" document (excel file) contains all planned actions on the static document, classified by target audience, and aims to be the compilation document for all actions carried out. The document is regularly updated to reflect all actions that are executed by all partners during VALUEWASTE's execution time.

Innovarum, as Communication Coordinator and responsible for the Task 10.1, included Communication and Dissemination Actions related to all Tasks of the Work Package 10 (Dissemination and Communication) in the Valuwaste **Dissemination and Communication Plan (D10.1)**.

That included Tasks **10.2 and 10.3 (Specific Communication Campaigns)**, whose responsible partners are: Servicios Urbanos de Murcia, S.A.U.-Servicios Ferrovial and Ayuntamiento de Murcia (Task 10.2) and Kalundborg Kommune and Ayuntamiento de Murcia (Task 10.3). As well as, Tasks **10.4** (Promotion of Project results) and **10.5** (Specific Communication Actions).

These four Tasks are explained below:

Task 10.2.and Task 10.3

Task 10.2: Educational campaign in Murcia (M9-M24)

Responsible partners: Servicios Urbanos de Murcia, S.A.U.-Servicios Ferroviales and Ayuntamiento de Murcia

The “Communication Campaign 1: Educational campaign in Murcia” started preparations on July 2019 (M9). The project partners responsible for this task are: Ayuntamiento de Murcia and Servicios Urbanos de Murcia, S.A.U.-Servicios Ferroviales.

As it is indicated at the end of this Report, the indicators and impact of this campaign will be further analysed in the D10.3: “Report on the preparation of Educational Campaign in Murcia”

Task 10.3. Citizens awareness campaign in Murcia and Kalundborg (M18-M37)

Responsible partners: Kalundborg Kommune and Ayuntamiento de Murcia

Murcia and Kalundborg’s municipalities are the responsible partners for this task. This campaign will not begin until July 2020.

As it is indicated at the end of this Report, the indicators and impact of this campaign will be further analysed in the D10.5: “Evaluation of the citizen awareness campaign”

Task 10.4. Promotion of project results to a targeted audience (M4-M48)

Responsible partner: Innovarum, Communication Coordinator.

During the first year of the project very few results have arisen from the project execution. Innovarum, as responsible partner for this task, is keeping track of the project partners actions and is working in close cooperation with the project coordinator, CETENMA, in order to maximize diffusion once results start to come out.

CETENMA has published an entry at the “Horizon Results Platform Pilot”: *Towards the utilisation of biowaste as a resource: a review of EU Policy on biowaste management*. The platform is now closed and will reopen sometime on October.

Specific actions included in the Task 10.4: Trade Shows and Fairs, technical publications/papers and attendance to high-level policy events.

The following section (*Review of the Valuwaste D&C Plan*) shows that Valuwaste has been already involved in Trade Shows, High level policy events and has three technical publications. Nevertheless, since the project still has not produced significant results, the actions were used for the general communication and presentation of the project and not for promotion of results.

Task 10.5. Communication (M4-M48)

Responsible partner: Innovarum, Communication Coordinator.

Innovarum is directly responsible for the execution of the following **actions included in the Task 10.5:**

1. Opening of the Project website
2. Mention to the project in Project partner’s websites
3. Creation of On-line social networks: (LinkedIn & Twitter),
4. Production of audio-visual materials and the visual identity.

Besides, **other communication actions** considered in this Task are: Attendance to conferences and the Final event on site (organised by CETENMA).

All actions related to these Tasks (Task 10.2 to 10.5) will be reviewed in detail in the next section, "**Review of the VW D&C Plan**".

2. Review of the Valuwaste D&C Plan (D10.1)

The following Section includes a review of all the communication and dissemination actions included and described in the Valuwaste Dissemination and Communication Plan (D10.1), which covers all the Tasks of the Work Package 10 (Dissemination and Communication).

The table below presents all the actions described in the Dissemination and Communication Plan, its leader partners and its targets:

Table 1: D&C Targets General Overview

	Final Target	Lead Partner	M12 (October 2019)	
1 - All target audiences				
			Status	
VALUEWASTE website & Blog - Integration of VALUEWASTE on partners' websites	500 visits/month, at least 30 posts	Innovarum	565 visits & 7 posts	
Social Media	300 followers (twitter), 100 followers (LinkedIn)	Innovarum	Twitter 186	LinkedIn 91
Audio-visual materials	2 videos			
Other informative materials	15 informative materials	Innovarum	9	
Media coverage	100 media coverages	All partners	37	
Final event	80-100 attendants			
EC Dissemination routes	4	Innovarum	4	
2 - General public				
			Status	
Communication Campaign 1 – Murcia	To be analysed	MU-FERR/Murcia	Starting	
Communication Campaign 2 – Murcia and Kalundborg	To be established	Kalundborg/Murcia		
3 - Policy makers				
			Status	
Meetings and interviews	5 meetings or interviews with policymakers	Murcia	5	
Attendance to high level policy events	5 events		2	
4 - Industry players				
			Status	
Trade shows and fairs	15 events attended	Innovarum	5	
5 - Academia				
			Status	
Technical publications Papers	5	Innovarum	3	
Workshops, conferences and congresses	10 events	Innovarum	20	

Target 1- All target audiences

We hereby describe the communication activities carried out so far for the Target 1:

VALUEWASTE website & Blog - Integration of VALUEWASTE on partners' websites

Figure 1: VW webpage

Website address: <http://Valuewaste.eu/>

The web is available in English, and the first version contained the following sections:

- **Home Page.** With a brief summary of the VALUEWASTE project and objectives.
- **Workplan.** a description of the work packages (objectives, leading partner and duration) together with a PERT diagram.
- **Partners.** This section shows each partner's brief description, role in VALUEWASTE, logo and website of the partner.
- **Our Friends.** dedicated to other projects related to VALUEWASTE, with their logo and link to their official website (SCALIBUR, RESURBIS, WATER2RETURN, RUN4LIFE, URBIOFIN, EMBRACED and SMART PLANT)
- **Available material.** This section hosts dissemination materials (poster, roll-up and project factsheet).
- **Media.** Media coverage of the project (video, articles in newspapers and podcasts).
- **News.** Posts internally elaborated by Innovarum and other partners concerning the project's development.
- **Footer.** The website contains the statement "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 818312", as well as the EU emblem.

On M10 (August 2019) some sections we updated:

- The "Partners" section was updated to "**Partners & Advisory Board**". It includes a description of the members that make the External Advisory Board of Valuwaste.

- The “**Our Friends**” section was also updated on M10. The tab title has not changed, the section now contains also information of Networks Valuwaste belongs to: Biorefine Cluster and EUBioNet.
- Valuwaste News section has been updated with news related to Valuwaste Project events and partners actions. Currently, the news section counts with 6 entries (or blog posts).

Project partner's websites

All project partners were provided in the Kick-off Meeting with a standard text to include in their respective official websites. Innovarum assured that by M3 (31 January 2019), a mention to VALUEWASTE project was included in all the partners' websites.

Table 2: Partner's mention to the Valuwaste Project in their webpages

Nº	Partner	Mention to the Valuwaste Project
1	Centro Tecnológico de la Energía y el Medio Ambiente	https://www.cetenma.es/works/Valuwaste/ https://www.cetenma.es/works/Valuwaste/?lang=en
2	Eurizon S.L.	http://www.innovarum.es/en/project/Valuwaste-en/ http://www.innovarum.es/es/project/Valuwaste-es/
3	Savonia University of Applied Sciences - Savonia-ammattikorkeakoulu oy	https://portal.savonia.fi/amk/en/rdi/rdi-projects-and-entrepreneurship/rdi-projects?id=1037
4	Servicios Urbanos de Murcia, S.A.U.-Servicios Ferroviario	http://www.murciaciudadostenible.es/es/reducir-reutilizar-reciclar/Valuwaste.htm http://www.murciaciudadostenible.es/es/
5	Ayuntamiento de Murcia	http://www.murciaciudadostenible.es/es/reducir-reutilizar-reciclar/Valuwaste.htm http://www.murciaciudadostenible.es/es/
6	Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón	https://www.itainnova.es/blog/proyectos-financiacion-publica/Valuwaste/
7	Unibio A/S	https://www.unibio.dk/press-release-how-waste-is-turned-into-food/
8	Agro Business Park A/S	https://www.agropark.dk/projekter/Valuwaste
9	Asociación Española de Normalización, (Spanish Association for Standardisation)	https://www.une.org/normalizacion/proyectos-de-idi/
10	Nutrient Recovery Systems bvba	http://www.nuresys.be/news.html
11	Ekobalans Fenix AB	https://www.ekobalans.se/sv/om-ekobalans2/nyhete/146-ekobalans-i-eu-projektet-Valuwaste
12	Ingeniería y Desarrollos Renovables, S.L.	https://inderen.es/eu-funded-project-Valuwaste/

Nº	Partner	Mention to the Valuwaste Project
13	GAIKER-IK4 Technology Centre	http://www.gaiker.es/cas/biodeteccion_proyectos.aspx
14	Entomo Agroindustrial S.L.	http://entomoagroindustrial.com/portfolio/Value-waste/ https://entomoagroindustrial.com/en/portfolio/Valuwaste/
15	Seah International	https://www.seah.net/en/seah-international-Valuwaste/
16	Kalundborg Kommune	https://symbiosecenter.dk/en/project/Valuwaste/
LT P - 16	Kalundborg Symbiose / Symbiosis Center	https://symbiosecenter.dk/en/project/Valuwaste/
17	European Biomass Industry Association	http://www.eubia.org/cms/projects-2/ongoing-projects/

Webpage visits: the measurable target

Webpage visits as well as the general performance of the Valuwaste webpage are tracked with Google Analytics.

Figure 2: VW webpage visits

Since the launching of the Valuwaste webpage in English on April 23th 2019 (M6), traffic has progressively increased. On October, the visits to the webpage were **565** (visits to the web only in the month of October).

Average monthly web traffic growth is 19% and it is expected to decrease and stabilize in the following months. The final Target for this action is to reach and maintain 500 webpage visits monthly. According to the above numbers, **Valuwaste webpage has already reached that number on October 2019 (565 visits). Thus, the challenge for the next year will be sustaining that traffic.**

A webpage opening attracts a high volume of traffic and visits. Maintaining and growing that volume afterwards is the challenge ahead.

With that challenge in mind, and in order to better measure traffic quality, Innovarum is also tracking the unique pageviews to the Valuwaste webpage:

Figure 3: VW webpage unique pageviews

"A **unique pageview**, as seen in the Content Overview report, aggregates pageviews that are generated by the same user during the same session" Google Analytics

Valuwaste Blog

Valuwaste Blog follows a structure of short to medium length posts. The topic of these posts is the activity of the Valuwaste project partners: the events they attend, the presentations they make, the meetings they organise... As well as relevant moments or important news related to the project. The blog posts published so far are:

1. Valuwaste Kick-off meeting (1,192 views).
2. Valuwaste joined the Biorefine Cluster Europe (246 views).
3. Agro Business Park presents Valuwaste to a Chinese Delegation (108 views).
4. ABP meets with The Trade Council from the Danish Ministry of Foreign Affairs (291 views).
5. Food Festival 2019: Northern Europe biggest food event (482 views).
6. Dansk Bioøkonomi Konference 2019 (507 views).
7. Valuwaste General Assembly (just published).

They can be read at: <http://Valuwaste.eu/news/>

Social media

Social media accounts are managed with Hootsuite. Content strategy is supported with Hootsuite, Twitter and LinkedIn Analytics, Google Alerts and organic web research.

Valuewaste Twitter account

VALUEWASTE project counts with an official Twitter account: @ValuewasteP

Figure 4: Valuewaste Twitter (23/10/2019)

To date, Valuewaste has in total 350 publications (tweets) in English and Spanish. Valuewaste twitter content includes:

1. Pictures related to its content.
2. Frames specifically designed for Valuewaste Social Media accounts.
3. Informative messages related to biobased products, waste management, innovative food ingredients...
4. News related to the project and to the project partners actions.
5. "Call to action" messages to redirect traffic to the Valuewaste webpage.
6. Common *hashtags* used: #Valuewaste #urbanbiowaste #biowaste #H2020 #circulareconomy #bioeconomy #alternativeproteins #fertilisers #insectprotein.
7. Project partners Twitter accounts are also mentioned when appropriate.
8. Project partners also actively mention @ValuewasteP in their tweets.

The Valuewaste Twitter content strategy also focuses on related *trending topics* such as: World Hunger, Climate Change, Environmental Challenges, Millennium Development Goals (MDG)... It produces content considering current global issues and conversations.

Figure 5: VW Tweets example

Figure 6: VW Twitter followers & growth

In October 2019, VALUEWASTE project Twitter account had 186 followers and followed 116 accounts. After the rapid growth that follows the opening of an account, growth is stabilising at around a 7-9% rate.

Valuewaste follower base counts with:

- Other H2020 projects a
- Projects related to the bioeconomy, waste management, circular economy...
- Associations and organization interested or involved with the bioeconomy or waste management.
- Research Centres and Universities
- Personal Twitter Accounts.

Valuewaste Twitter account follows:

- Friends Projects: Scalibur, WaysTup!, Resurbis, Run4Life, Urbiofin, Embraced or SmartPlan.
- Other H2020 projects.
- Its project partners.
- Organizations/associations of interests to the project. For example, the networks it belongs to: Biorefine Cluster and EuBioNet.

VALUEWASTE project counts with an official LinkedIn account is: ValuEWASTE H2020 Project.

Figure 7: ValuEWASTE LinkedIn

ValuEWASTE LinkedIn content is tailored to fit the style, structure and target audience of LinkedIn. Thus:

- ValuEWASTE LinkedIn posts have longer messages and more links and resources available.
- Content and tone are curated to fit LinkedIn style.
- Some examples of shared publications or content are:
 - Report: *EU Commission, 2017, New European Consensus on Development 'Our World, Our Dignity, Our Future'*
 - Report: *FAO, 2018, Food loss and waste and the right to adequate food: Making the connection, Right to Food Discussion Paper*

Besides, LinkedIn content strategy also considers all the points above for the Twitter content strategy.

Figure 8: LinkedIn Posts examples

ValueWaste H2020 Project
77 seguidores
1 mes • Cualquiera

#Valuewaste #Objetivo3
https://lnkd.in/fV_uAG6

Entomo AgroIndustrial
656 seguidores
1 mes • Cualquiera

Objetivo 3 ValueWaste H2020 Project

Realizar el diseño de una planta de tratamiento de residuos orgánicos ... ver más

OBJETIVO 3 VALUEWASTE

valuewaste.eu

8

ValueWaste H2020 Project
77 seguidores
3 semanas • Cualquiera

Agro Business Park A/S and Unibio presented the #Valuewaste project at the "Food waste and Business opportunities" event organised by INBIOM

Link: <http://ow.ly/Jp2Q50vVdrB>

#Wastemanagement #Bioeconomy #Biowaste #Urbanbiowaste #Circularconomy #FoodWaste #FoodandFeed

Ver traducción

13

ValueWaste H2020 Project
77 seguidores
1 mes • Editado • Cualquiera

Did you have time to take a look to the "New European Consensus on Development 'Our World, Our Dignity, Our Future'"?

The #EU and its #MemberStates will promote resource #Efficiency and #SustainableConsumption and production, including the sustainable management of chemicals and #waste, with a view to decoupling economic growth from environmental degradation and enabling the transition to a #circularEconomy"

#Valuewaste project seeks to contribute to EU #Sustainability through its revalorising processes of biowaste into new valuable products.

Full PDF: <http://ow.ly/EBQr50vJscg>

Ver traducción

NEW EUROPEAN CONSENSUS ON DEVELOPMENT 'OUR WORLD, OUR DIGNITY, OUR FUTURE'

#CircularEconomy

8

ValueWaste H2020 Project
77 seguidores
1 mes • Editado • Cualquiera

#Valuewaste se une al cluster #europeo Biorefine Cluster Europe

#Valuewaste joins the #BioRefine Cluster #Europe

"The #BiorefineClusterEurope interconnects projects and people within the domain of #biobased resource recovery, striving to contribute to a more sustainable #ResourceManagement in the framework of #CircularEconomy systems.

<https://lnkd.in/f9mWQkr>

#biobased #biowaste #bioeconomy
#Circularconomy CETENMA Centro tecnológico, Innovarum, Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Ferrovial, Ayuntamiento de Murcia, ITAINNOVA Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón, Unibio, Agro Business Park A/S, Cooperation and International Relations, NuReSys (Nutrient Recovery System), #Ekobalans (Sweden), @INDEREN (Ingeniería y desarrollos renovables), Entomo AgroIndustrial, #SeahInternational, Kalundborg Kommune and European Biomass Industry Association
#ValueWaste #ValueWasteProject

#Biowaste #Circularconomy #Bioeconomy #Alternativeproteins
#FoodIngredients #Fertilisers #ValueStreams #H2020 #Murcia #Kalundborg #EU #EUCommission

Ver traducción

VALUEWASTE JOINS THE BIOREFINE CLUSTER EUROPE

#BiorefineCluster

10

Figure 9: VW LinkedIn Followers

On October of 2019, VALUEWASTE project LinkedIn account had 91 followers. VALUEWASTE LinkedIn account opened on June 2019 (it has been active for 5 months). It experimented a rapid growth at the opening (from June to September 2019).

Growth is starting to decrease and is expected to stabilise in the following semester.

Audio visual materials

This action refers to 2 planned videos:

1. Valuewaste Presentation video (first part of the project).
2. Final execution video to present at the Final Event (No specific schedule yet).

Innovarum will start the production of the first video (Valuewaste Presentation video) in December 2019.

Other informative materials

During the first year of the project, Innovarum elaborated and defined the visual identity of the project and produced a total of 9 informative materials:

1. Poster 2019
2. Roll up 2019
3. Technical Fact sheet 2019
4. Dissemination KIT: Jun-19
5. Process 1 informative factsheet: Jul-19
6. Process 2 informative factsheet: Jul-19
7. Process 3 informative factsheet: Jul-19
8. Valuewaste Basic Presentation: Sep-19
9. Valuewaste Slideshow: Sep-19

Visual Identity of the Valuwaste Project

VW Poster and Roll up 2019

VALUEWASTE
Unlocking new value from urban biowaste

VALORISATION of urban biowaste Every EU citizen generates on average **120 million tonnes** annually in the EU
200 kg of urban bio waste every year

VW proposes an integrated system for urban biowaste valorisation into key strategic products for the EU

THREE VALORISING LINES OF URBAN BIOWASTE

Selective collection in cities	Biowaste Treatment in Waste Management Plant	Treatment by Industrial Partners & Intermediate Product	Final Marketable Product
URBAN BIOWASTE	METHANE	MICROBIAL PROTEINS	FOOD
	DISGESTATE	INSECT PROTEINS	FEED
	EFFLUENT	NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS	BIODERIVED FERTILISER

EXPECTED IMPACTS OF VALUEWASTE

- 1,200 tonnes of urban biowaste annually valorised in Murcia (Spain)
- More than 40 tonnes of proteins yearly produced
- Valuable nutrients for EU agriculture are recovered from residual streams
- Regional perception of citizens on urban biowaste as a local source of valuable materials
- Evidence-based support for future EU policies, towards the implementation of the EU Circular Economy strategy

Two very different European municipalities are involved in the VALUEWASTE project: **Kalundborg (DK)** and **Murcia (ES)**

SYSTEM REPLICABLE ACROSS EUROPE

CALL: H2020 - CE-SFS-25-2018 | BUDGET: 10 ME | DURATION: 48 months (Nov'18 - Oct'22)
WORK-PLAN: 12 work packages | PARTNERS: 17 from 6 EU countries (ES, DK, FR, FI, BE, SE)

Project Coordinators: Gemma Castejón & Martín Soriano - CETENMA
Dissemination Manager: María Serrano - INNOVARIUM

www.valuewaste.eu @valuewasteP

PROJECT PARTNERS: CETENMA, innovarium, SAVONIA, Ayuntamiento de Murcia, ITANNING, UNIBIO, UNE, NuReSys, ERBIOALIAS, GAZTEP, entome, seah, etc.

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VALUEWASTE
Unlocking new value from urban biowaste

VALUEWASTE proposes an integrated system for urban biowaste valorisation into key strategic products for the EU

THREE VALORISING LINES OF URBAN BIOWASTE

Selective collection in cities	Biowaste Treatment in Waste Management Plant	Treatment by Industrial Partners & Intermediate Product	Final Marketable Product
URBAN BIOWASTE	METHANE	MICROBIAL PROTEINS	FOOD
	DISGESTATE	INSECT PROTEINS	FEED
	EFFLUENT	NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS	BIODERIVED FERTILISER

- Increase the EU self-sufficiency in proteins and critical raw materials
- Demonstration at semi-industrial, scale of three valorisation processes
- Generation of new business models on urban biowaste management

17 partners from 6 countries

Project demonstrated in 2 EU cities: Murcia (Spain), Kalundborg (Denmark)

PROJECT PARTNERS: CETENMA, innovarium, SAVONIA, Ayuntamiento de Murcia, ITANNING, UNIBIO, UNE, NuReSys, ERBIOALIAS, GAZTEP, entome, seah, etc.

www.valuewaste.eu @valuewasteP

Horizon 2020 European Union funding for Research & Innovation. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 818312.

Fact sheet-Technical: 2019 (English & Spanish)

The image shows two fact sheets. The left one is titled 'Unlocking new value from urban biowaste' and includes sections for 'FACTSHEET', 'BASIC INFORMATION', 'NEED FOR INNOVATION URBAN BIOWASTE MANAGEMENT', and 'VALUEWASTE CONCEPT: PROVIDING KEY RESOURCES'. The right one is titled 'VALUEWASTE METHODOLOGY' and 'VALUEWASTE OBJECTIVES', featuring a map of Europe, a list of partners from various countries, and contact information.

Dissemination KIT: Jun-19

Innovarum prepared a “Dissemination Kit” that was distributed to the rest of the partners so that they can effectively participate in the project’s dissemination and communication. This Dissemination Kit includes:

- VALUEWASTE Poster (digital format – web and print version)
- VALUEWASTE Factsheet (digital format, ES and EN, web and print version)
- VALUEWASTE Roll-up (digital format, ES and EN, web and print version)
- Basic guidelines on proper use of the provided material (printing instructions)
- Partners obligations: minimal D&C actions, acknowledge EU funding, advance notification of dissemination of results, protocol for D&C actions compilation, measured parameters, etc.
- Basic template for D&C actions compilation

Informative factsheets for the General Public-One per process of the Valuwaste project: Jul-19 (English)

VALUEWASTE
Unlocking new value from urban biowaste

Is it possible? Nutrients from biogas

1. Selective collection in cities
The most common organic residues (biowaste)

2. Waste Management Plant
Biogas production through the processing of urban biowaste (anaerobic digestion)

3. Treatment by industrial partners (biogas U-value?)
Highly efficient industrial feed units (methane, nutrients and proteins). These factories make use of methane for generating other products.

4. The final product
Highly efficient biogas production (methane, nutrients and proteins). These factories make use of methane for generating other products.

FOOD INGREDIENT: PROTEINS
Proteins are essential nutrients for the human body. We get them through the intake of a wide variety of foods: legumes, cereals, vegetables, fruits and animal-based foods.

In Europe, almost 60% of the protein intake is animal-sourced (meat, eggs, dairy, fish and seafood, etc.)

SUSTAINABILITY
Massive production of animal-sourced protein is responsible of significant environmental impact: use of water, CO₂ emissions and land use for feed production.

The valorisation of biowaste into food and feed protein remains one of the most promising alternatives for a more sustainable protein supply chain.

Food & Feed ingredients

THE SOLUTION: ValueWaste
The U-value[®] technology will be scaled-up during ValueWaste project, making use of methane obtained from the anaerobic digestion of urban biowaste to produce protein and other food and feed ingredients.

Partners involved: UNIBIO (DK) and SEAH (FR)

Basic information
Call: CE 975-22-209
Duration: 48 months (2019-2022)
Total budget: 4,038,835 €
EU Contribution: 1,875,472 €

Consortium
17 partners from: BE, DK, FR, ES, IE, IT, NL, PT, SE, UK

Coordinator
Technological Centre for Energy and the Environment
ICT Energy, Spain

Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation
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VALUEWASTE
Unlocking new value from urban biowaste

Feeding our soils: fertilisers of the future

1. Selective collection in cities
The most common organic residues (biowaste)

2. Waste Management Plant
Urban biowaste is subject to anaerobic digestion and treatment. The feed effluent is treated for nutrient recovery.

3. Treatment by industrial partners (Nitrogen and Phosphorus)
Recovery of nitrogen and phosphorus from the wastewater effluents on municipal and industrial substrates.

4. The final product: soil fertilisers
Nutrients are treated and granulated to reuse in soil fertilisers.

KEY FERTILISER COMPONENTS
Nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) are the three major nutrients that plants need for growing.

N Nitrogen is a core component of plant cells and tissues, and essential for producing the phytochemicals.

P Phosphorus is needed for normal development. It is also used for photosynthesis, transfer of energy and regulation.

Agricultural production is sustained by the use of fertilisers that contain nutrients needed for plant growth.

SUSTAINABILITY
Phosphorus is mainly obtained from phosphate rock, a limited and depletable resource. In addition, the waste of phosphorus from human activities may cause environmental problems if not wisely water accumulated.

Nitrogen: the production of nitrogen fertilisers is highly energy demanding and it is directly linked to fossil fuels, is limited and cost-intensive resource.

THE SOLUTION: ValueWaste
We will implement a combined approach for producing sustainable fertilisers from liquid effluents characterised for its high nitrogen and phosphorus content. That is, an environmentally friendly, highly nutrient soil fertilizer.

Partners involved: NUREN (BE), ENCE (AN) and SEAH (FR). COOP FERTILISER SERVICES (ES) and UNIBIO (DK).

Basic information
Call: CE 975-22-209
Duration: 48 months (2019-2022)
Total budget: 4,038,835 €
EU Contribution: 1,875,472 €

Consortium
17 partners from: BE, DK, FR, ES, IE, IT, NL, PT, SE, UK

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VALUEWASTE
Unlocking new value from urban biowaste

Insects protein alternative: a second life to waste

1. Selective collection in cities
The most common organic residues (biowaste)

2. Waste Management Plant
Processing and grinding of urban biowaste.

3. Treatment by industrial partners (Insecte Agri-food)
Insects are fed with the processed and dried biowaste. After the growing phase (2-8 weeks), insects are harvested, washed and fed dried.

4. The final product: feed ingredients
Feed ingredients are obtained from crickets in general and beet.

THE VALUE OF INSECTS
Some insects are valuable sources of protein, comparable to meat and fish. In addition, insects also provide polyunsaturated fatty acids (omega fatty acids), minerals and vitamins (iron, calcium, B12, ...). Black Soldier Flies, the insects used in ValueWaste Project, are not vectors for diseases, or pests for crops or animals.

SUSTAINABILITY
Massive production of animal-sourced protein is responsible of significant environmental impact: use of water, CO₂ emissions and land use for feed production.

Insects are a promising alternative and sustainable source of protein.

THE SOLUTION: ValueWaste
An insect farm will be installed in a waste treatment plant in Purice (Spain). This farm has the potential to: Convert biowaste into a final product of around 40% protein, 30% fat and 1% calcium. Accept any kind of organic waste, including meat fish, and products, vegetables.

Partners involved: ENTOMO AGRICOLA INDUSTRIAL (ES), DESER FERMENAL SERVICES (ES) and NUREN (BE).

Basic information
Call: CE 975-22-209
Duration: 48 months (2019-2022)
Total budget: 4,038,835 €
EU Contribution: 1,875,472 €

Consortium
17 partners from: BE, DK, FR, ES, IE, IT, NL, PT, SE, UK

Coordinator
Technological Centre for Energy and the Environment
ICT Energy, Spain

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Valuewaste Basic Presentation: Sep-19 (English & Spanish) & Valuewaste Slideshow: Oct-19 (English)

VALUEWASTE
Unlocking new value from urban biowaste

AUTHORS:
AFFILIATION:
EVENT AND DATE:

Grant agreement ID: 818312

Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation
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VALUEWASTE
Unlocking new value from urban biowaste

WEBPAGE AND SOCIAL MEDIA

QR codes for website, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook.

Twitter: @Valuewaste
LinkedIn: Valuewaste H2020 Project
www.valuewaste.eu

Both documents were sent to the VALUEWASTE partners so they could publish them in their websites.

General media coverages

Apart from the 2 press releases, project partners have generated:

- 4 radio interviews
- 1 TV interview
- 8 news/articles in newspapers/magazines (online)
- 24 news or entries about Valuewaste in webpages/blogs.

Valuewaste project partners have been notoriously active, helping to generate a total of 37 media coverages during the first year of the project:

Table 3: VW media coverages

When	What/Where	Who	Link
08/10/2018	Innovation Network for Bioresources -	ABP	https://inbiom.dk/inbiom/nyheder/horizon2020-succes?Action=1&currentPage=2&M=NewsV2&PID=19747
08/10/2018	LA VERDAD DE MURCIA - El Conenedor marron se instala en Murcia	MU-FERROVIAL	El contenedor marrón se instalará a partir de septiembre en el barrio ...
21/11/2018	Webpage Ayuntamiento de Murcia - Murcia acoge la reunión transnacional destinada a cambiar la gestión de residuos y hallar nuevas formas de alimentación	MURCIA	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=49831
21/11/2018	7TVREGIONDEMURCIA - Murcia probará el contenedor de residuos orgánicos en los barrios que más reciclan	MU-FERROVIAL	Murcia probará el contenedor de residuos orgánicos en los barrios ...
22/11/2018	Ecoticias- Murcia lidera un proyecto pionero para transformar los residuos orgánicos en proteínas, piensos y fertilizantes	CETENMA	https://www.ecoticias.com/residuos-reciclaje/189821/Murcia-lidera-proyecto-pionero-transformar-residuos-organicos#.W_zr_PQwYu0.twitter
22/11/2018	20 MINUTOS - El quinto contenedor se instala en Murcia	MU-FERROVIAL	El quinto contenedor se instalará a partir de septiembre en el barrio ...
23/11/2018	Innovation Network for Bioresources -	ABP	
23/11/2018	LA SER - Murcia implanta el quinto contenedor	MU-FERROVIAL	Murcia implantará en septiembre el quinto contenedor de residuos ...
28/11/2018	La Verdad (Innovation supplement)- Convertir residuos urbanos en comida, una apuesta que contribuye a la economía circular	CETENMA	
28/11/2018	Webpage Ayuntamiento de Murcia - Murcia participa en un proyecto europeo que permitirá revalorizar 1.800 toneladas de residuos sólidos urbanos y reducir 540 toneladas de CO2 al año	MURCIA	https://www.murcia.com/noticias/2019/02/17-murcia-participa-en-un-proyecto-europeo-que-permitira-revalorizar-1800-toneladas-de-residuos-solidos-urbanos-y-reducir-540-t.asp
11/12/2018	INDEREN WEB NEWS- INDEREN is taking part in the VALUEWASTE project	INDEREN	
11/12/2018	Aragón Radio - interview with Salvador Izquierdo	ITAINNOVA	
16/12/2018	LA VERDAD DE MURCIA- La planta de Cañada Hermosa tendrá una granja de larvas para producir proteínas	MU-FERROVIAL	La planta de Cañada Hermosa tendrá una granja de larvas para ...

When	What/Where	Who	Link
23/12/2018	ARAGONHOY.NET - ITAINNOVA participa en el proyecto VALUEWASTE para la recuperación de recursos de los residuos orgánicos generados por ciudadanos	ITAINNOVA	http://www.aragonhoy.net/index.php/mod.noticias/mem_detalle/relmenu.46/id.235820
23/12/2018	ELPERIODICODEARAGON.COM - Itainnova participa en la recuperación de recursos de residuos orgánicos	ITAINNOVA	https://www.elperiodicodearagon.com/noticias/aragon/itainnova-participa-recuperacion-recursos-residuos-organicos_1332309.html
26/12/2018	Residuos Profesional- Murcia, campo de pruebas del proyecto europeo de valorización de residuos orgánicos VALUEWASTE	CETENMA	https://www.residuosprofesional.com/murcia-proyecto-Valuewaste/
26/12/2018	Aragón Radio - interview with Salvador Izquierdo	ITAINNOVA	
27/12/2018	Pacto de Alcalde Webpage-Proyecto H2020 VALUEWASTE	MURCIA	http://www.pactocaldesremurcia.es/?q=blog/proyecto-h2020-Valuewaste
27/12/2018	Pacto de Alcalde Webpage-LA PLANTA DE CAÑADA HERMOSA TENDRÁ UNA GRANJA DE LARVAS PARA PRODUCIR PROTEÍNAS	MURCIA	http://www.pactocaldesremurcia.es/?q=blog/la-planta-de-ca%C3%B1ada-hermosa-tendr%C3%A1-una-granja-de-larvas-para-producir-prote%C3%Adnas
27/12/2018	Webpage Ayuntamiento de Murcia - Murcia participa en un proyecto europeo que permitirá revalorizar 1.800 toneladas de residuos sólidos urbanos y reducir 540 toneladas de CO2 al año	MURCIA	https://centromedios.murcia.es/PUBLICO/NotaPrensa/Default.aspx?pldPagina=25&pldNoticia=50801
01/01/2019	Kokonaisratkaisu bioarvoketjun hyödyntämiseksi- SAVONIA UNIVERSITY Magazine	SAVONIA	https://portal.savonia.fi/amk/fi/tutustu-savoniaan/organisaatio-ja-johtaminen/savonian-viestinta/savonian-sanomat
17/01/2019	Curiosity 7 RM- VALUEWASTE: Un nuevo proyecto europeo en torno a los residuos	CETENMA	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FMNgFz6eKQI
18/01/2019	La Verdad- Una marca de ropa, una plataforma de venta 'online' y un proyecto agrario, premios Emprendedor del Mes	ENTOMO	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/marca-ropa-plataforma-20190118122128-nt.html
19/01/2019	La Verdad- La harina de mosca te hace emprendedor	ENTOMO	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/comunidad/2019/01/19/harina-mosca-emprededor/989801.html
04/03/2019	La Verdad- Murcia tendrá la primera granja de larvas de mosca de España	ENTOMO	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/murcia/2019/03/04/murcia-tendra-primera-granja-larvas/1001732.html

When	What/Where	Who	Link
04/03/2019	LA OPINION DE MURCIA- El proyecto de I+D 'Valuewaste', cofinanciado por la Comisión Europea, permitirá crear en la Planta de Tratamiento de Residuos de Cañada Hermosa	MU-FERROVIAL	Murcia tendrá la primera granja de larvas de mosca de España - La ...
11/03/2019	La Opinión- Se crea en Cehegin un centro para tratar materia orgánica usando insectos	ENTOMO	https://www.laopiniondemurcia.es/municipios/2019/03/11/crea-cehegin-centro-investigacion-tratar/1004033.html
12/03/2019	La Verdad-Crean el primer centro investigador para tratar materia orgánica usando insectos	ENTOMO	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/otros-municipios/crean-primer-centro-20190312012418-ntvo.html
02/04/2019	Heraldo de Aragón - Proyecto Europeo sobre residuos tan valiosos que hasta se pueden comer	ITAINNOVA	https://www.heraldo.es/noticias/sociedad/2019/04/02/residuos-tan-valiosos-que-se-pueden-comer-1306870.html
03/04/2019	Cadena Ser - Entrevista a Diego Amores. Emprendedor del Año	ENTOMO	https://play.cadenaser.com/audio/011RD01000000221231/
04/05/2019	Valuewaste Proyecto financiado por la UE	INDEREN	https://inderen.es/es/Valuewaste-proyecto-financiado-por-la-ue/
26/05/2019	INDEREN asistió a la reunión de lanzamiento del proyecto Valuewaste	INDEREN	https://inderen.es/es/inderen-reunion-lanzamiento-proyecto-Valuewaste/
08/08/2019	NUESTRO PROYECTO VALUEWASTE SE UNE AL CLÚSTER EUROPEO BIOREFINE	CETENMA	https://www.cetenma.es/nuestro-proyecto-Valuewaste-se-une-al-cluster-europeo-biorefine/
08/08/2019	Biorefine Cluster Europe-Project section	CETENMA	https://www.biorefine.eu/Valuewaste
10/09/2019	Valuewaste project presentation: fertilisers of the future	INDEREN	https://inderen.es/Valuewaste-project-presentation-fertilisers-of-the-future/
18/09/2019	Presentación del proyecto Valuewaste: fertilizantes del futuro	INDEREN	https://inderen.es/es/presentacion-proyecto-Valuewaste-fertilizantes-del-futuro/
10/10/2019	Valuewaste project presentation: insects protein a second life to urban waste	INDEREN	https://inderen.es/Valuewaste-project-presentation-insects-protein-a-second-life-to-urban-waste/

EU Communication routes

The Valuwaste Project is present in four EU Communication and Dissemination platforms:

1. **Cordis:** Valuwaste: Unlocking new Value from urban bioWaste (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/218515/en>)

The Project Coordinator (CETENMA) published and updated content of the Valuwaste project specifically in the three following platforms:

2. **Horizon Results Platform (Pilot):** “Towards the utilisation of biowaste as a resource: a review of EU Policy on biowaste management”
3. **European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform:** “Valuwaste: Unlocking new Value from urban bioWaste”. Link: <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/good-practices/Valuwaste-unlocking-new-value-urban-biowaste>
4. **EIP-Agri:** “Unlocking new VALUE from urban bioWASTE”. Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/unlocking-new-value-urban-biowaste>

Target 2 - General public

Households and businesses as generator of urban biowaste

1. **Communication Campaign 1 – Murcia:** the communication campaign is scheduled to officially start this month (October 2019)
2. **Communication Campaign 2 – Murcia and Kalundborg:** Start M18 (July 2020)

NOTE: The Communication Campaigns above will be summarised in future Reports:

*The **Communication Campaign 1 – Murcia** will be further analysed in the D10.3: “Report on the preparation of Educational Campaign in Murcia”*

*The “**Communication Campaign 2 – Murcia and Kalundborg** will be further analysed in the D10.5: “Evaluation of the citizen awareness campaign”*

Target 3 – Policy makers

Policy makers

Meetings and interviews with policy makers:

Valuewaste partners scheduled the following meetings or interviews with policy makers:

Table 4: VW actions. Meetings and interviews with policy makers

Partner	Meeting with	Date	Links	Feedback
MURCIA	Presentation of the Valuwaste project to the Covenant of Mayors during the event “ <i>Presentación Plan Mitigación Cambio Climático Ayuntamiento de Murcia</i> ”	23/11/2018	https://www.laverdad.es/murcia/ciudad-murcia/murcia-dota-estrategia-20190318005012-ntvo.html	People were surprised by the characteristics and goals of the project but interested. They had questions on the steps the project would follow.
MURCIA	Working group on the “ <i>Plan Mitigación Cambio Climático Ayuntamiento de Murcia</i> ” with the participation of the Covenant of Mayors - Distribution of informative brochures about the value waste	23/11/2018		Policy makers had questions on the project and doubts on the safety of the final product for human consumption. They also had inquiries about the legal procedures to bring the product to the market.
CETENMA	Presentation of the VW project during the visit of the government of Murcia Region (including its president and employment/environment Counselor) and companies.	26/11/2018	https://twitter.com/CETENMA/status/1067071651383296001	Local government from Murcia expressed support to the project. The local government has defined a Circular Economy strategy and is working to create a specific plan for the Murcia city. Policy makers showed interest in the biowaste selective collection process, many municipalities will join the initiative in the future and will need advice from the project. Policy makers also congratulated the work of CETENMA and Entomo Agroindustrial as relevant companies that support the sustainable development of the city of Murcia.

Partner	Meeting with	Date	Links	Feedback
ABP	Presentation for and meeting with The Danish Agriculture & Food Council	18/12/2018		Representants from the Danish Agriculture & Food Council listened to the presentation of the project and had questions on food safety and legal procedures.
ABP	The Trade Council from the Danish Ministry of Foreign Affairs - The Danish Trade Office in Barcelona	29/08/2019	http://spanien.um.dk/da/eksporttraadet/spanien-som-marked/messer%20og%20eksportfremstoed/	Policy makers in the meeting were interested in the development of the project so far and had questions about the pilot cities of the project (Murcia and Kalundborg).

Attendance to high level policy events

During the first year of the project, CETENMA participated in two high level policy events:

1. 22/11/2018: “Experts Workshop on Urban Circular Bioeconomy” in Brussels.

General goal of the event: collect inputs on how to draft, finance, implement and assess an urban circular bioeconomy strategy

Type of participation: participation in the debate and introduction of the Valuwaste project.

Link: <https://www.resurbis.eu/EU-workshop-on-circular-economy>

2. 06/12/2018: “Meeting of the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste” in Brussels.

General goal of the event: identify, measure, understand and find solutions to deal with food waste.

Type of participation: participation, Valuwaste project slides included in the presentation delivered by Karen FABBRI, Head of Sector (DG RTD F3): “FOOD 2030: A Policy Framework to Future-Proof our Food Systems”

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_waste/eu_actions/eu-platform_en

Picture 1: Experts Workshop on Urban Circular Bioeconomy

Target 4 - Industry players

Waste and wastewater treatment companies & other H2020 projects

Trade shows and fairs:

In total, Valuwaste has been represented in 2 trade shows that were relevant for the project:

1. On 26/09/2019, INDEREN attended to **EXPOBIOMASA** 2019.

Link: <https://www.expobiomasa.com/info-practica>

Type of participation: Oral presentation of the project and distribution of editions of the Valuewaste article in the RETENMA magazine (Special issue on bioenergy, September 2019; <https://www.retema.es/revistas/especial-bioenergia-jLyeG>)

Size of the event: 16,540 attendants and 540 exhibitors.

2. On the 02/10/2019 MU-FERROVIAL attended to **Ecofira** 2019.

Link: <http://ecofira.feriavalencia.com/en/ecofira-feria-internacional-de-las-soluciones-medioambientales/>

Type of participation: company booth, promotion with the Valuewaste roll up and brochures. **Size of the event:** 103 exhibitors.

Target 5 - Academia

Researchers, universities, and RTOs.

Technical publications/ Papers:

Description of the action: as indicated in the GA and in the D10.1, this action covers: (1) the publication of the relevant results in the evolution of the VALUEWASTE project in specialised national and international magazines on waste, urban waste, waste management, recycling, reusing, circular economy or bio-economy; and (2) the publication of papers.

During the first year of the project there were publications belonging to the first category (Specialised magazines):

1. **18/12/2018. Ymparisto Journal, Magazine on Finnish regional and environmental research:** "The magazine publishes high-quality referee articles in the fields of social and cultural theoretical and social science environmental research."
Article: *Kokonaisratkaisu bioarvoketjun hyödyntämiseksi*
Ymparisto Journal Webpage: www.aluejaymparisto.journal.fi
2. **11/09/2019. RETENMA, Technical environmental magazine.** No. 216 July/August 2019 - *VALUEWASTE convertirá residuos urbanos en comida* (CETENMA). Link: <https://www.retema.es/revistas/julio-agosto-Lp5Fl>
3. **25/09/2019. RETENMA, Technical environmental magazine.** No. 217 (Bioenergy special issue) *Especial Bioenergía 2019 - Valorización integral de biorresiduos en el marco del proyecto Valuewaste.* (INDEREN). Link: <https://www.retema.es/revistas/especial-bioenergia-jLyeG>

Workshops, conferences, and congresses

ValueWaste project partners have participated in 22 “workshops, conferences and congresses” linked to the project during the first year of the project. The events attended took place in different countries and provinces across Europe.

Table 5: Workshops, conferences, and congresses

When	Event	Partner	Link	Where	Type of participation	No. of event attendants ¹
23/11/2018	II Workshop on the action plan for the climate and sustainable energy 2030	CETENMA		Murcia, Spain	Round table. Presentation of the ValueWaste project, promotion with the Project roll-up.	23
21/02/2019	I Foro Internacional de Innovación, Sostenibilidad y Economía	MU FERROVIAL and MURCIA		Murcia, Spain	Presenting ValueWaste to the attendees (individual talks). Distribution of informative brochures about ValueWaste and presentation of the Roll-up.	50
07/03/2019	Workshop on Circular Economy	CETENMA		Murcia, Spain	Oral presentation on the ValueWaste project during the first circular economy sectorial forum in Murcia (Spain)	30
11/03/2019	Workshop on Climate change mitigation plan meeting	CETENMA		Murcia, Spain	Round table and oral presentation of the ValueWaste project.	15
14/03/2019	AEMA. JORNADA EMPRESA Y MEDIOAMBIENTE	MU FERROVIAL		Spain	Oral presentation of the ValueWaste project, online brochure distribution, informative brochures distribution onsite.	20
27/03/2019	GREEN CITIES 2019 Malaga	ENTOMO	http://greencities.malaga.eu/opencms/export/sites/greencities/content/documentos/greencities/Programa-ELEVATOR-PITCH-.pdf	Malaga, Spain	Oral presentation (“Valorización industrial de materia orgánica usando insectos”), description of the ValueWaste project	170 companies, 3,800 professionals

¹ Number of attendants is approximative

When	Event	Partner	Link	Where	Type of participation	No. of event attendants ¹
04/04/2019	I JORNADA DE NUTRICIÓN NUTRIN	ENTOMO	http://www.integaonline.com/i-jornada-de-nutricion-nutrin/	Lorca, Spain	Oral presentation of the project	30
12/04/2019	BBI JU INFO DAY 2019	ABP	https://www.bbi-europe.eu/events/bbi-ju-info-day-2019	Brussels, Belgium	Promotion of the Valuwaste project and use of dissemination materials: roll up, brochure. Presentation of the project to attendees (individual talks).	300
26/04/2019	Course "Circular Economy management"	CETENMA	https://www.cetenma.es/ya-puedes-inscribirte-al-curso-gratuito-que-te-formara-como-gestor-en-economia-circular/	Cartagena, Spain	Collaboration with training course on circular economy and oral presentation of the valuwaste project as an example.	25
08/05/2019	Advisory Board Scalibur Project (H2020)	CETENMA	https://twitter.com/CETENMA/status/1126147096489361408	Lund, Sweden	Participation in EU Project Advisory Board and oral presentation of the Valuwaste Project	30
03/06/2019	World Circular economy forum	SAVONIA UNIVERTISTY	https://www.sitra.fi/en/projects/world-circular-economy-forum-2019/	Online	Participation in the webinars. Valuwaste mentioned and promoted in the online materials given to participants	2,207
06/06/2019	Event EU Green Week-Biowaste Management and Environmental Sustainability in EU - Think green every day!	EUBIA	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/eu-green-week-partner-event-biowaste-management-and-environmental-sustainability-in-eu-think-green-tickets-58575687458#	Brussels, Belgium	Event organisation and oral presentation of the Valuwaste project. Round table.	50
16/06/2019	ISPIM Conference	SAVONIA UNIVERTISTY	https://www.ispim-innovation-conference.com/	Florence, Italy	Valuwaste poster presentation	700
25/06/2019	"Circular Bioeconomy Days 2019"	ABP and UNIBIO	http://conferences.au.dk/circularbioeconomydays2019/programme/	Aarhus University, Foulum, Denmark	Event organised by ABP. Oral presentation on the Valueaste project by UNIBIO, Valuwaste online poster promotion.	50

When	Event	Partner	Link	Where	Type of participation	No. of event attendants ¹
27/08/2019	Food waste and Business opportunities	ABP and UNIBIO	https://danishfoodinnovation.dk/event/kick-off-forretningsgoerelse-af-foedevarespild/	Denmark	Valuewaste Oral Presentation - <i>Fra organisk affald til fødevareingrediens ved Michael Jensen, Unibio/From organic waste to food ingredient by Michael Jensen, Unibio</i>	56
06/09/2019	Food Festival	ABP	https://www.foodfestival.dk/en/	TANGKROGEN · AA RHUS	Oral presentation on the " Food and lifestyle scene" and presentation of the Valuewaste project. Presentation of samples of Uniprotein® from ValueWaste partner Unibio	70 attendants to the presentation. More the 30,000 attendees to the festival
25/09/2019	Danish Bioeconomy Conference	ABP	https://inbiom.nemtilmeld.dk/images/descriptions/13164/DanskBioekonomiKonference2019-invitationogprogram2019-29.08.19.pdf	Denmark	Roll-up and Uniprotein sampe for exhibition.	60
03/10/2019	Jornadas Económicas Locales en Murcia	MURCIA	https://www.um.es/observalocal/?p=33591	Murcia	Oral presentation of the project and on opportunities and challenges in waste.	40
03/10/2019	Kick-Off meeting: project WausTUP!	INDEREN		Murcia	Oral presentation of the project	30
10/10/2019	I Foro Comprometidos con una Región de Murcia Sostenible	MURCIA	http://7tvregiondemurcia.es/la7-reune-a-una-veintena-de-expertos-en-el-i-foro-comprometidos-con-una-region-de-murcia-sostenible/	Murcia	Oral presentation of the project	30
25/10/2019	CLIMATHON MURCIA 2019	CETENMA, MURCIA, MU-FERROVIAL and ENTOMO	https://climathon.climate-kic.org/	Murcia	Oral presentation of the project and distribution of project brochures	73

Picture 2: Dansk Bioeconomy Conference

Picture 3: I Foro Comprometidos con una Región de Murcia Sostenible

Picture 4: Food Festival 2019

General feedback from the conferences, workshops, and congresses:

Feedback from the attendants who received informative content or who were present in the oral/poster presentations delivered by the project partners of the Valuewaste project was in general positive. Attendants to events were interested in the characteristics of the project and on its objectives. There were questions on the extraction processes, on the safety of the final product and, especially on the last months, on the development of the Campaign in Murcia (Spain).

3. Additional Actions and quality assessment of all the actions taken

Additional actions taken

ValuEWaste Partners sometimes contribute to the communication of the project with actions that are not possible to categorize under the original indicators established in the D&C Plan (D10.1). Relevant actions that are important to mention in this regard are actions related to Networks and Associations:

- ValuEWaste became part of the **Biorefine Cluster Europe on August 2019**. Currently, ValuEWaste is a full member of the network: <https://www.biorefine.eu/ValuEWaste>
- ValuEWaste became part of **EUBIONET** “The European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet)” on September 2019: <https://eubionet.eu/>

Being a member of this type of clusters and organizations is good for networking and access to relevant interesting events. Besides, it has a positive impact on ValuEWaste webpage SEO positioning and social media follower's growth.

Quality assessment of all the actions taken: first year of the project

Online strategy: webpage and social media

The online strategy of the D&C Plan of the ValuEWaste Project is based on: its webpage, its social media accounts, blog publications, online media coverages of the project partners, presence in Networks with online activity (Biorefine Cluster and EuBioNet) as well as on the support that the online EU Communication routes (Cordis, EIP-Agri webpages...) offer. In general, **the strategy is consolidated, and it is helping achieve the targets and impact expected in the D&C Plan.**

Besides, **project partners offer active support to all online communication actions initiated** by the Communication Partner (Innovarum) and/or the Project Coordinator (CETENMA). The efficient support of the 17 partners of the project (universities, companies of different sizes, research centres... etc) is a key part of the ultimate success of the online Communication of the Project.

Finally, an area that can be improved is the blog. The content of the blog would benefit from longer posts that talk about processes of the project or about specific issues related to waste management, zero hunger, bioeconomy... etc. It would also be positive to include collaborative

content with friend projects like Scalibur or WaysUp! In this respect, **blog content strategy can be reviewed and updated.**

Audio visual materials

All audio-visual materials follow the visual identity of the project and include relevant curated content for the audiences they are intended for. They are the result of **a throughout design and content development process**. Besides, materials are always reviewed several times both by the Communication Partner (Innovarum) and the Communication Coordinator (CETENMA).

Looking forward into the next year, it is important to produce a video presentation for the Valuewaste project. This will support both the online and offline strategy of the project.

Media Coverages

The number of publications after 12 months of project progress is high (37 in total). However, most of the coverages belong to news in webpages/blogs (66%).

As the project develops, it would be **beneficial to start including more publications or interviews in renewed newspapers or radio/TV interviews** (which are also more difficult to schedule and organise).

Meetings and interviews with policy makers & High-level policy events

On the one hand, meetings and interviews with policy makers are carried out mainly by CETENMA (project coordinator), MURCIA (Municipality of Murcia) and Agro Business Park A/S. On the other hand, CETENMA, as project coordinator, is the only partner that has taken part so far in high-level policy events.

Workshops, conferences and congresses

As mentioned before, Valuewaste project partners are very active and involve themselves in many Communication actions. Moreover, they sometimes even develop their own communication actions independently.

For example, EUBIA was one of the organisers of the **“EU Green Week- Biowaste Management and Environmental Sustainability in EU - Think green every day”**

This was a relevant event to the project organised together by EUBIA, Biorefine Cluster Europe, Scalibur, Valuewaste, Grassification and Agrimax. It offered an opportunity to present the project to different stakeholders as well as a chance to collaborate between other related projects (Scalibur, Grassification and Agrimax).

Another recent example of the level of engagement was the **“CLIMATHON Murcia 2019”**, a big event on waste management collection and valorisation with conferences and workshops that took place in Murcia the 25 of October. Four project partners attended to the event (CETENMA, MURCIA, MU-FERROVIAL and ENTOMO) and presented and promoted the project.

Trade shows and fairs

Trade shows and fairs are actions meant mostly for the promotion of results of the project ([Task 10.4\) in the D&C Plan](#)). Even though there are still very few results, some project partners have started attending and participating in this type of events (MU-FERROVIAL and INDEREN).

However, they have used these events to present the project (as a Communication Action). In the future, as results come out, **the consortium will need to start engaging more in this type of actions.**

Additionally, it will be important to focus on the relevance of the event to the Valuwaste project. This is an isolated case, but on the 30/03/2019 MURCIA participated in the “Feria de Vehículo Eléctrico Ciudad de Murcia” (<https://movielectrica.es/>). Ultimately, this event could not be counted as an action for the project due to its topic, which was not relevant to Valuwaste.

Technical publications/ Papers

So far there are three “technical publications”. These publications focus on presentations of the project and on the description of some of its processes. In the future, **once results start to come out, it will be positive to start publishing new papers and technical publications.**

4. Conclusions: progress overview

Task 10.1.

Development of a Dissemination & Communication Plan (M1-M3)

As explained at the beginning of this document, the D&C Plan was produced by Innovarum according to schedule (M1-M3). The Dissemination and Communication Plan captures all the actions included in the Tasks 10.2, 10.3, 10.4 and 10.5.

The next update (D10.4) is expected on month 25 of the project (November 2020): “Communication activities: how to face the second half of the project”

Task 10.2. & Task 10.3

Specific Communication Campaigns

- The “Communication Campaign 1: Educational campaign in Murcia” started preparations on July 2019 (M9), so progress at M12 (October 2019) is still limited. The indicators and impact of this campaign will be further analysed in the D10.3: “Report on the preparation of Educational Campaign in Murcia”
- The “Campaign 2: Citizens awareness campaign in Murcia and Kalundborg” will start on M18 and last to M37. The indicators and impact of this campaign will be further analysed in the D10.5: “Evaluation of the citizen awareness campaign”

Task 10.4

Promotion of project results to a targeted audience (M4-M48)

Specific actions included in the Task 10.4: Trade Shows and Fairs, technical publications/papers and attendance to high-level policy events.

As this document presents, Valuwaste has participated in Trade Shows, attended to High-policy events and counts with technical publications. Nonetheless, so far this type of actions has been used for general communication purposes only and not for the dissemination of results.² Thus, the progress of this specific Task (promotion of results) is limited.

Task 10.5

Communication (M4-M48)

Specific actions included in the Task 10.5: opening of the Project website and mention to the project in Project partner’s websites, creation of On-line social accounts (LinkedIn & Twitter), production of audio-visual materials, attendance to conferences and the Final event on site (organised by CETENMA).

² The project has produced very few results so far.

The progress of the execution of the actions included in this Task 10.5 (presented below) is the most relevant. This is normal for the first year of the project: presenting the project, its goals, impact... etc is the key starting point.

All actions: progress overview

The figure below showcases the current state and progress of the D&C actions:

Figure 10: VW D&C Target accomplishment progress overview

Table 6: VW D&C actions (D10.1) accomplishment ratio

ACTION	TARGET	M12	Accomplishment %
VALUEWASTE website visits /monthly	500	565	113%
Blog Posts	30	7	23%
Social Media Twitter	300	186	61%
Social Media LinkedIn	100	91	91%
Audio Visual Materials	2	0	0%
Other informative materials	15	9	60%
Media coverage	100	37	36%
EC Dissemination routes	4	4	100%
Meetings and interviews with policy makers	5	5	100%
Attendance to high level policy events	5	2	40%
Trade shows and fairs	15	2	13%
Technical publications/ Papers	5	3	40%
Workshops, conferences & congresses	10	22	220%

After 12 months of the Valuwaste Project execution, **approximately 65% of the numerically measurable indicators established in the D&C Plan (D10.1) are accomplished**. That is, after 25% of project development, 65% of the Dissemination and Communication Actions are completed.

More specifically, Valuwaste has reached or surpassed the numerical indicators for the following actions:

- EC Dissemination routes
- Meetings and interviews with policy makers
- Workshops, conferences & congresses.

However, it is important to note that a rapid progress at the beginning of the execution of a D&C Plan is expected. The launching of a webpage, social media accounts, kick-off events, informative materials... etc, together with the start of all project partners work creates many Communication Actions opportunities.

The **challenge** for the next year will be **to maintain the level of activity and engagement** between project partners and between the Valuwaste community. Additionally, the project still needs to **increase its impact and accomplish the remaining targets** of the D&C Plan (D10.1).

Besides, in order to maximize the impact of the actions taken, it will be important **to keep on improving the quality** of the actions that the Valuwaste project undertakes. This includes webpage content; increase media coverages in relevant newspapers, magazines, tv/radio; as well as the dissemination of precise results (when the time comes).

In order to do that, the Dissemination and Communication campaign will have to rely and support: the activity of all project partners, the results that the project will start to produce, and the Communication Campaigns described included on Task 10.2 and 10.3.

Additionally, Innovarum (as Communication Partner) has scheduled the following actions:

Communication Coordinator: Action points

1. Innovarum will keep attracting traffic to the VW webpage through different channels. As the project develops, new materials will be available, the project will be better known, and Social Media followers will increase. Therefore, webpage traffic will also increase.
2. Innovarum will review the content strategy for the blog and will include longer publications about relevant topics as well as collaborative publications if possible. This action will also support the growth of the webpage monthly visits.
3. In order to maximize the impact of the Murcia campaign (Launching in November 2019), Innovarum is considering translating the Valuewaste webpage to Spanish by M16 (February).
4. A collaborative approach between related projects can generate a higher impact and attract a bigger audience. Now that the project is running and all basic communication tasks are completed, Innovarum will contact Valuewaste friend projects (Scalibur, WaysTup!...etc) to suggest the organization a workshop/webinar together on a common topic (waste management...etc) on M13 (November 2019).
5. Innovarum will coordinate the production of an introductory video of the Valuewaste Project starting on M14 (December 2019).
6. Innovarum will also support an encourage all partners to generate more media coverages in renowned magazines, newspapers, TV/radio for the general audience.
7. As the project start to produce results, it will be important to focus on actions for the adequate public dissemination and promotion. Innovarum, as Communication Coordinator, will track this process.

Annexes

Annex 1: VW D&C actions and Public Deliverables Schedule

M12	Oct-19	Deliverable 10.2: Communication activities: first year of VALUEWASTE project
M13	Nov-19	Contact Scalibur and other fellow projects: collaborative action Deliverable 10.3: Report on the preparation of Educational Campaign in Murcia
M14	Dec-19	Production VW video
M15	Jan-20	
M16	Feb-20	Web translation to Spanish (if approved)
M17	Mar-20	
M18	Apr-20	
M19	May-20	
M20	Jun-20	
M21	Jul-20	
M22	Aug-20	
M23	Sep-20	
M24	Oct-20	
M25	Nov-20	Deliverable 10.4: Communication activities: how to face second half of the project
M26	Dec-20	
M27	Jan-21	
M28	Feb-21	
M29	Mar-21	
M30	Apr-21	
M31	May-21	
M32	Jun-21	
M33	Jul-21	
M34	Aug-21	
M35	Sep-21	
M36	Oct-21	Deliverable 10.5: Evaluation of the citizen awareness campaign
M37	Nov-21	
M38	Dec-21	
M39	Jan-22	
M40	Feb-22	
M41	Mar-22	
M42	Apr-22	
M43	May-22	
M44	Jun-22	
M45	Jul-22	
M46	Aug-22	
M47	Sep-22	
M48	Oct-22	

Annex 2: Valuewaste D&C actions evolution (M1-M6)

Action		Final Target	Lead Partner	Month of the Project												Sparkline
1 - All target audiences				M1 (Nov 2018)	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6 (April 2019)						Sparkline	
				Status												
1A	VALUEWASTE website & Blog - Integration of VALUEWASTE on partners' websites	500 visits/month, at least 30 posts	Innovarum	Web not opened yet	Web not opened yet	Web not opened yet		Web not opened yet								
1B	Social Media	300 followers (twitter), 100 followers (LinkedIn)	Innovarum	Twitter: 57 LinkedIn: Not opened	Twitter: 73 LinkedIn: Not opened	Twitter: 81 LinkedIn: Not opened	Twitter: 90 LinkedIn: Not opened	Twitter: 101 LinkedIn: LinkedIn	Twitter: 110 LinkedIn: LinkedIn							
1C	Audio-visual materials	2 videos														
1D	Other informative materials	15 informative materials	Innovarum	3	3	3	3	3	5							
1E	Media coverage	100 media coverages	All partners	10	20	23	23	27	29							
1F	Final event	80-100 attendants														
1G	EC Dissemination routes	Presence in 4 routes	Innovarum	1	1	3	3	3	3							
2 - General public (households and businesses as generator of urban biowaste)				M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6				Sparkline			
2A	Communication Campaign 1 – Murcia		Ayuntamiento de Murcia & FERROVIAL	Status												
2B	Communication Campaign 2 – Murcia and Kalundborg		Ayuntamiento de Murcia & Kalundborg	Status												
3 - Policy makers				M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6				Sparkline			
3A	Meetings and interviews	5 meetings or interviews with	Murcia	3	4	4	4	4	4							
3B	Attendance to high level policy events	5 events		2	2	2	2	2	2							
4 - Industry players (waste and wastewater treatment companies & other H2020 projects)				M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6				Sparkline			
4A	Trade shows and fairs	15 events attended	Innovarum	Status												
				0	0	0	0	0	0							
5 - Academia (researchers, universities and RTOs)				M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6				Sparkline			
5A	Technical publications/ Papers	5	Innovarum	Status												
5B	Workshops, conferences and congresses	10 events	Innovarum	1	1	1	2	6	8							

Annex 3: Valuwaste D&C actions evolution (M7-M12)

Action	Final Target	Lead Partner	Month of the Project						Sparkline						
			M7 (May 2019)	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12 (October 2019)							
1 - All target audiences															
VALUEWASTE website & Blog -	500 visits/month, at least 30 posts	Innovarum	Status												
1A Integration of VALUEWASTE on partners' websites			0/ 1 post	146/ 1 post	213/ 1 post	360 and 4 posts	472 and 5 posts	565 and 7 posts							
1B Social Media	300 followers (twitter), 100 followers (Linkedln)	Innovarum	Twitter 120	Linkedin Not opened	Twitter 135	Linkedin 13	Twitter 145	Linkedin 40	Twitter 156	Linkedin 50	Twitter 166	Linkedin 77	Twitter 186	Linkedin 91	
1C Audio-visual materials	2 videos														
1D Other informative materials	15 informative materials	Innovarum	5	7	7	8	9	9							
1E Media coverage	100 media coverages	All partners	29	29	31	31	31	37							
1F Final event	80-100 attendants														
1G EC Dissemination routes	Presence in 4 routes	Innovarum	3	3	3	4	4	4							
2 - General public (households and businesses as generator of urban															
			M7 (May 2019)	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12 (October 2019)	Sparkline						
2A Communication Campaign 1 – Murcia		Ayuntamiento de Murcia & FERROVIAL			Preparation months	Preparation months									
2B Communication Campaign 2 – Murcia and Kalundborg		Ayuntamiento de Murcia & Kalundborg													
3 - Policy makers															
			M7 (May 2019)	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12 (October 2019)	Sparkline						
3A Meetings and interviews	5 meetings or interviews with policymakers	Murcia	4	4	4	5	5	5							
3B Attendance to high level policy events	5 events		2	2	2	2	2	2							
4 - Industry players (waste and wastewater treatment companies & other															
			M7 (May 2019)	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12 (October 2019)	Sparkline						
4A Trade shows and fairs	15 events attended	Innovarum	0	0	0	0	1	2							
5 - Academia (researchers, universities and RTOs)															
			M7 (May 2019)	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12 (October 2019)	Sparkline						
5A Technical publications/ Papers	5	Innovarum	0	0	0	0	2	3							
5B Workshops, conferences and congresses	10 events	Innovarum	9	13	13	16	18	20							